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PERCEIVE

**Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections
through AI and Virtual Experiences**

D1.1. Operational plan, Progress Report and Evaluation Report

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Project information

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Project Duration: 36 months

Project website: <https://perceive.eu>

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PERCEIVE consortium

No.		Short name	Institution name	Country
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2	BEN	FORTH	IDRYMA TECHNOLOGIAS KAI EREVNAS	Greece
3	BEN	ANAMNESIA	ANAMNESIA	France
3.1	AE	IMKI	IMKI	France
4	BEN	NTNU	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	Norway
5	BEN	FRAUNHOFER	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV	Germany
6	BEN	MIC-MANN	MINISTERO DELLA CULTURA MANN MUSEUM (MIC-MANN)	Italy
7	BEN	OSL-MUNCH	OSLO KOMMUNE MUNCH MUSEUM (OSL- MUNCH)	Norway
8	AP	AIC	THE ART INSTITUTE OF CHICAGO US	USA
9	AP	HOVERLAY	Hoverlay US	USA
10	AP	HSLU	FACHHOCHSCHULE ZENTRALSCHWEIZ - HOCHSCHULE LUZERN CH	Switzerland
11	AP	V&A	VICTORIA AND ALBERT MUSEUM UK	UK

Executive summary

PERCEIVE aims at creating a new way to preserve, perceive, curate, exhibit, understand and access colored Cultural Heritage collections and Digital Artworks. Therefore, promoting their re-appropriation. These collections are a priority because of their high fragility - requiring shared methods to preserve and exhibit them; the complexity of their study; the significance of their proper communication to future generations. PERCEIVE will support the shaping of a European common identity around the concepts of “care” and “diversity” and strengthen the digital market for the creative industries.

Document History

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V0.1	31/05/2023	First draft released	CNR
V0.2	13/07/2023	Review	ANAMNESIA
V0.3	28/07/2023	Final version released	CNR
V1.0	31/07/2023	Submitted version	CNR

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Introduction

The kickoff meeting was the first occasion for the project partners to discuss the planning of activities in each WP in order to guarantee an efficient and smooth running of activities. One of the aspects presented and discussed was the internal organization of the consortium, including operational and reporting processes, communication protocols, and formation about standards, technical quality control, procedures for risk monitoring, decision-making and conflicts resolution. The following chapters summarize mainly the outcomes of the kickoff meeting that form the Operational Plan.

Project organization, roles and responsibilities

Figure 1. Project scheme.

Project Coordinator

The Coordinator shall be the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the Coordinator shall be responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations under the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement;
- keeping the address list of Members and other contact persons updated and available;
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the Granting Authority;

- transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned;
- administering the financial contribution of the Granting Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks described in Section 7.2 of the Consortium Agreement;
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims;
- providing a copy of the Grant Agreement and its Annexes to the Associated Partners.

If one or more of the Parties is late in submission of any Project deliverable, the Coordinator may nevertheless submit the other 'Parties' Project deliverables and all other documents required by the Grant Agreement to the Granting Authority in time.

If the Coordinator fails in its coordination tasks, the General Assembly may propose to the Granting Authority to change the Coordinator.

The Coordinator shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of any other Party or of the consortium, unless explicitly stated otherwise in the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement.

The Coordinator shall not enlarge its role beyond the tasks specified in the Consortium Agreement and in the Grant Agreement.

The Project Scientific Board (PSB)

The Project Scientific Board plans, organizes and coordinates in general all research activities of the project, constantly overseeing the effectiveness in achieving the expected results and efficiency in carrying out the various activities on time. It includes the control of Data Management Plan (DMP – D2.1) for making data/research outputs findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR). SB could be advised by the Advisory Board and by the project Working Groups.

The Project Scientific Board is chaired by the Scientific Coordinator and consists of the Project Coordinator, one scientific representative of each Party leading each Work Package (WP), one representative of each Working Group, according to the Consortium Plan, and, if necessary, additional members appointed by the Project Committee. These individuals are hereinafter referred to as Scientific Board Members.

External Persons may be invited to attend the Scientific Board without voting rights.

The Project Coordinator will ensure that a non-disclosure agreement is executed between all Parties and External Persons that will attend Scientific Board's meetings.

Party No.	Acronym	Representative	Contact
1	CNR	Sofia Pescarin - Project Coordinator	sofia.pescarin@cnr.it
5	Fraunhofer	Holger Graf - Scientific Coordinator	holger.graf@igd.fraunhofer.de
1	CNR	Ivana Cerato (WP1)	ivana.cerato@cnr.it

6	MIC-MANN	Cristiana Barandoni (WP2)	paolo.giulierini@cultura.gov.it
2	FORTH	Sophia Sotiropoulou (WP3)	sophiaso@iesl.forth.gr
5	Fraunhofer	Pavel Rojtberg (WP4)	pavel.rojtberg@igd.fraunhofer.de
2	FORTH	Panos Trahanias (WP5)	trahania@ics.forth.gr
1	CNR	Daniele Ferdani (WP6)	daniele.ferdani@cnr.it
4	NTNU	Sony George (WP7)	sony.george@ntnu.no
3.1	IMKI	Florent Michel (WP8)	f.michel@imki.tech
		Nr 5 Representative of Working Groups	To be Appointed by G.A.

Table 1. The list of the Scientific Board Members.

Project Management Board (PMB)

The PMB is the supervisory body for the execution of the Project and reports to / be accountable to the General Assembly. It is chaired by the Project Coordinator and consists of the Scientific Coordinator, the Innovation Manager, the WP leaders and, if necessary, additional members appointed by the General Assembly. These individuals are hereinafter referred to as Management Board Members.

External Persons may be invited to attend the Management Board without voting rights.

The Coordinator chairs all meetings of the PMB, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds.

Minutes of Management Board meetings, once accepted, are sent by the Coordinator to the General Assembly Members for information.

The tasks of the PMB are:

- prepare the meetings, propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly according to Section 6.3.1.2 of the consortium agreement;
- seek a consensus among the Parties;
- be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly;
- monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project.

Party No.	Acronym	Representative	Contact
1	CNR	Sofia Pescarin - Project Coordinator (WP1, WP6 Representative)	sofia.pescarin@cnr.it

5	Fraunhofer	Holger Graf - Scientific Coordinator (WP4 Representative)	holger.graf@igd.fraunhofer.de
6	MIC-MANN	Paolo Giulierini (WP2 Representative)	paolo.gulierini@cultura.gov.it
2	FORTH	Sophia Sotiropoulou (WP3, WP5 Representative)	sophiaso@iesl.forth.gr
4	NTNU	Jon Yngve Hardeberg (WP7 Representative)	jon.hardeberg@ntnu.no
3	Anamnesia	Simon Sappa – Innovation Manager (WP8 Representative)	s.sappa@anamnesia.com

Table 2. The list of the Project Management Board Members.

In addition, the Management Board collects information at least every 6 months on the progress of the Project, examines that information to assess the compliance of the Project with the Consortium Plan and, if necessary, proposes modifications of the Consortium Plan to the General Assembly.

The Management Board shall:

- support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables;
- prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the Granting Authority in respect of the procedures of the Grant Agreement Article 17 and Annex 5 Section “Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility” and of Section 8 of this Consortium Agreement.

In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the General Assembly, the Management Board shall advise the General Assembly on ways to rearrange tasks and budgets of the Parties concerned. Such a rearrangement shall take into consideration any prior legitimate commitments which cannot be cancelled.

Advisory Board (AB)

An Advisory Board (AB) is appointed and steered by the Project Management Board. The AB assists the Scientific Board and facilitate the decisions made by the General Assembly.

The project has identified experts and innovators coming from main and representative institutions. They are involved in the project and every year, among them, the General Assembly votes for 6 members who sit in the scientific Advisory Board of the project, in line with its advancement. The experts who already gave their availability and letter of support during the project presentation, and who confirmed their availability, have been involved during the first year of the project, as listed in the Description of Action.

The Project Coordinator ensures that a non-disclosure agreement is executed between all Parties and each AB member.

The Project Coordinator provides the minutes of the AB meetings and submit them to the Project Committee.

General Assembly (GA)

The **General Assembly (GA)** is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium. It consists of one representative of each Party (hereinafter General Assembly Member).

Party No.	Acronym	Representative	Contact
1	CNR	Sofia Pescarin	sofia.pescarin@cnr.it
2	FORTH	Sophia Sotiropoulou	sophiaso@iesl.forth.gr
3	Anamnesia	Simon Sappa	s.sappa@anamnesia.com
3.1	IMKI	Florent Michel	f.michel@imki.tech
4	NTNU	Jon Yngve Hardeberg	jon.hardeberg@ntnu.no
5	Fraunhofer	Holger Graf	holger.graf@igd.fraunhofer.de
6	MIC-MANN	Paolo Giulierini	paolo.giulierini@cultura.gov.it
7	OSL-MUNCH	Irina Sandu	irina.sandu@munchmuseet.no
8	AIC	Giovanni Verri	gverri@artic.edu
9	Hoverlay	Nicolas Robbe	nicolas.robbe@hoverlay.com
10	HSLU	Richard Wetzel	richard.wetzel@hslu.ch
11	V&A	Lucia Burgio	l.burgio@vam.ac.uk

Table 3. The list of the General Assembly Members.

Each General Assembly Member shall be deemed to be duly authorized to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in Section 6.3.1.2. of this Consortium Agreement.

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the General Assembly, unless decided otherwise in a meeting of the General Assembly.

The Parties agree to abide by all decisions of the General Assembly. This does not prevent the Parties from exercising their veto rights, according to Section 6.2.4.1, or from submitting a dispute to resolution in accordance with the provisions of Settlement of disputes in Section 11.8.

The Associated Partners are excluded from voting on and vetoing the following decisions of the General Assembly (6.3.1.2) and therefore are not counted towards any respective quorum:

- Financial changes to the Consortium Plan
- Distribution of EU contribution among the Beneficiaries
- Decisions related to Section 7.1.4 of this Consortium Agreement

Regarding unanimity or majority decisions, only Members with voting rights regarding the item are taken into account (e.g., Section 6.2.2.8).

The General Assembly shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out herein.

In addition, all proposals made by the Management Board shall also be considered and decided upon by the General Assembly.

The following decisions shall be taken by the General Assembly:

Content, finances and intellectual property rights

- Proposals for changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Granting Authority
- Changes to the Consortium Plan
- Modifications or withdrawal of Background in Attachment 1 (Background Included)
- Additions to Attachment 3 (List of Third Parties for simplified transfer according to Section 8.3.2)

Evolution of the consortium

- Entry of a new Party to the Project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party
- Withdrawal of a Party from the Project and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal
- Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under this Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement
- Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party
- Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party
- Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the Project and measures relating thereto
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for a change of the Coordinator
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project
- Proposal to the Granting Authority for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement

Breach, defaulting party status and litigation

- Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under this Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement
 - Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party
 - Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party
 - Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the consortium and measures relating thereto
 - Steps to be taken for litigation purposes and the coverage of litigation costs in case of joint
 - Claims of the parties of the consortium against a Party (Section 4.2, Section 7.1.4)
- #### Appointments

On the basis of the Grant Agreement, the appointment if necessary of:

- Management Board Members
- Advisory Board Members
- Working Group members

Work Package Leaders

WP leaders coordinate the work and oversee the execution and progress of the Tasks within each WP; they are also responsible for the quality check and review of deliverables before submission

The current list of the WP leaders is shown in the table below. Any modifications must be communicated to the project coordinator and project manager.

Work Packages		Representative	Contact
1	Coordination and Management	CNR ISPC – Ivana Cerato	Ivana.cerato@cnr.it
2	Scenarios: needs, requirements and training	MIC MANN – Cristiana Barandoni	cristiana.barandoni@gmail.com
3	Material Modelling and Data Management	FORTH - Sophia Sotiropoulou	sophiaso@eap.gr
4	Perceive IBR / AI core	Fraunhofer - Holger Graf	holger.graf@igd.fraunhofer.de
5	Perceive platform: tools and services	FORTH - Sophia Sotiropoulou	sophiaso@eap.gr
6	Perceive Experiences	CNR ISPC – Daniele Ferdani	Daniele.ferdani@cnr.it
7	Assessment	NTNU - Jon Yngve Hardeberg	jon.hardeberg@ntnu.no
8	Innovation (Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation)	Anamnesia / IMKI - Laura Martel	l.martel@imki.tech

Table 4. The list of the WP leaders.

Other key roles

Innovation Manager - Simon Sappa (ANAMNESIA - s.sappa@anamnesia.com)

The Innovation Manager is responsible for the identification of the innovation potential of the exploitable results of the project.

Project Manager - Ivana Cerato (CNR ISPC – ivana.cerato@cnr.it)

The Project manager assist the coordinator in the day-by-day management of the GA, supports the coordinator with the collection of the collection of reports and deliverables, assists the coordinator in the financial management of the project, collects and verifies the financial statements from the

partners, supports partners with the preparation of financial reports, administrative and legal issues, supports the organization, preparation and follow up of periodical meetings.

Reports & payment requests¹

For the preparation and submission of reports and for payment requests, the Consortium should refer to:

- Funding & tender opportunities Portal
 - [Online Manual](#)
 - [Reference Documents](#)
- Grant Agreement n. 101061157
 - Data Sheet Section 4. Reporting, payments and recoveries
 - Art. 6 Eligible and ineligible costs and contributions
 - Art. 21 Reporting
 - Art. 22 Payments and recoveries — Calculation of amounts due
- Consortium Agreement
 - Art. 4.2 Specific responsibilities for Associated Partner(s)
 - Art. 7 Financial provisions

To comply with project reporting, the Consortium must update and prepare:

- [Continuous Reporting](#)
- Regular updates on the status of the project
- [Periodic report: Technical Report \(Part A and B\) and Financial Report](#)
- Periodic report on the progress of works and claimed costs

Figure 2. Reporting scheme.

Continuous Reporting²⁻³

At the beginning of the project, the Continuous Reporting Module has been activated. During the project, the Consortium shall update:

¹ Data Sheet Section 4. Reporting, payments and recoveries, Grant Agreement n. 101061157

² Art. 21.1 Continuous reporting, Grant Agreement n. 101061157

³ Data Sheet Section 4.1 Continuous reporting, Grant Agreement n. 101061157

- **project summary**
- **deliverables**
- **milestones**
- **critical risks**
- **program-specific monitoring information**

How to submit: Beneficiaries must update the information on the Continuous Reporting Module in the Grant Management System. Associated Partners and Affiliated Entity must update the items on the template for the Periodic Report provided in the Annex I and send it to the Coordinator.

The Continuous Reporting Module is automatically compiled to create Part A of the Periodic Technical Report.

Periodic reports ⁴⁻⁵

The PERCEIVE project is divided in two reporting periods with two internal progress reports to monitor the project's progress:

- 1st Internal Reporting Period: months 1-9
- **1st Reporting Period: months 1-15 (Interim)**
- 2nd Internal Reporting Period: months 16-26
- **2nd Reporting Period: months 16-36 (Final)**

The complete schedule of reporting periods is shown in the figures below.

Reporting					Payments	
Reporting periods			Type	Deadline	Type	Deadline (time to pay)
RP No	Month from	Month to				
					Initial prefinancing	30 days from entry into force/10 days before starting date – whichever is the latest
1	1	15	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Interim payment	90 days from receiving periodic report
2	16	36	Periodic report	60 days after end of reporting period	Final payment	90 days from receiving periodic report

Figure 3. Reporting and payments overview.

⁴ Art. 21.2 Periodic reporting: Technical reports and financial statements, Grant Agreement n. 101061157

⁵ Data Sheet Section 4.2 Periodic reporting and payments, Grant Agreement n. 101061157

Associated Partners who receive funds from the National Guarantee Fund shall follow the rules set by their Financing Authority.

Figure 5. Report process.

No.	Short name	Country	National Guarantee Fund
8	AIC	USA	NO
9	HOVERLAY	USA	NO
10	HSLU	Switzerland	YES
11	V&A	UK	YES

Table 5. Associated partner.

Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS)⁶⁻⁷

The CFS will have to be produced if the requested EU contribution is above the threshold of EUR 430 000. It will have to be issued by an independent auditor (or, for public bodies, public officer).

How to submit: It must be uploaded as a PDF scanned copy using the [template](#) available on [Portal Reference Documents](#).

No.	Short name	Estimated Total eligible costs
1	CNR	€ 585.383,75
2	FORTH	€ 643.750,00
4	NTNU	€ 701.250,00

⁶ Art. 24.2 Certificate on the financial statements (CFS), Grant Agreement n. 101061157

⁷ Data Sheet Section 4.3 Certificates, Grant Agreement n. 101061157

5	FRAUNHOFER	€ 753.901,25
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Table 6. Beneficiaries likely to have to submit CFS.

Reporting process

The periodic reporting in the Grant Management System opens at the end of each reporting period and the deadline for submission is 60 days.

The Beneficiaries shall:

- make sure that the information in the Continuous Reporting Module is updated
- complete their own Financial Statements
- sign and submit to the Coordinator the Financial Statements.

The Affiliated Entity must:

- supply its Beneficiary with a blue-ink signed paper Financial Statement; the Beneficiary must then fill in the information in the system and sign and submit.

The Coordinator must:

- review and explicitly approve the periodic report of all Beneficiaries. If needed, send back a Financial Statement to a Partner for further changes, or unlock the Technical Report for editing
- upload Part B of the Technical Report
- submit all parts of the report to the Granting Authority.

The Granting Authority will either:

- **accept** the report and start preparing the payment or
- **ask for changes** to it — which means that the process described above starts again.

Figure 6. Reporting process.

Beneficiary termination reporting⁸

If one of the Beneficiaries has to leave the Consortium, the Coordinator has to prepare a termination report (Technical Report Part B and Financial Report) and a report on the distribution of payments to this Beneficiary in the Grant Management System.

Payment⁹⁻¹⁰

When the Granting Authority approves the payment, the amount due will be paid out to the Coordinator within 90 days of receiving the report.

To receive the payment from the Coordinator, the Beneficiaries and Affiliated Entity must complete the table and enter the information in the EU form provided in the Calculation model for Financial Report (Annex II), which will be signed by the bank officer.

Internal and external communication

Project members area, templates and mailing lists

All project partners have access to the **Member Area**, the reserved repository for partners we will use to share all the documents related to the project. The repository is handled by CNR using Microsoft SharePoint and will be available for the project partners during the lifetime of the project and beyond.

The member area is organized in different folders, and it allows partners to store, quickly find and work collaboratively on project documents, keep track of revisions and different versions released. It also includes a dedicated folder [[Templates](#)] where the standard project templates are stored. Specifically, the following templates are available:

Name of the template	Location
Deliverable template	PERCEIVE Deliverables template.docx
Minute template	PERCEIVE meeting-MINUTES-Template.docx
EU-funding-CITATION-sentence	EU-funding-CITATION-sentence.docx
INSTITUTION - presentation - template	Perceive-INSTITUTION-presentation-template.pptx
KEYNOTE - presentation - template	Perceive-KEYNOTE-presentation-template.pptx
WP - presentation - template	Perceive-WP-presentation-template.pptx
WG - presentation - template	PERCEIVE-WG-presentation-template.pptx

Table 7.

⁸ Consortium Agreement Art. 3.2 Duration and Termination

⁹ Art. 22 Payments and recoveries, Grant Agreement n. 101061157

¹⁰ Consortium Agreement Art. 7 Payments

In order to guarantee and efficient communication among all project partners and ensure that the communications reach the correct people involved in different parts of the project, CNR has prepared a contacts list excel file that identifies all people involved in the project activities, their role in the project and contact details. The contacts' file is stored in the Members area, in GENERAL folder and it is updated. The project coordinator and project manager, who are responsible for keeping the file up to date, are informed about all modifications made by the partners. Furthermore, CNR has created mailing lists that allow partners to convey information efficiently:

Mail	Reference	Description
perceive-ga@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	GA	includes contacts of people involved in GA
perceive-pmb@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	PMB	includes contacts of people involved in PMB
perceive-psb@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	PSB	includes contacts of people involved in PSB
perceive-wp1@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WP 1	includes contacts of people involved in WP
perceive-wp2@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WP 2	includes contacts of people involved in WP
perceive-wp3@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WP 3	includes contacts of people involved in WP
perceive-wp4@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WP 4	includes contacts of people involved in WP
perceive-wp5@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WP 5	includes contacts of people involved in WP
perceive-wp6@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WP 6	includes contacts of people involved in WP
perceive-wp7@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WP 7	includes contacts of people involved in WP
perceive-wp8@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WP 8	includes contacts of people involved in WP
perceive-wg1-polychromy@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WG 1	includes contacts of people involved in WG
perceive-wg2-paintings@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WG 2	includes contacts of people involved in WG
perceive-wg3-textiles@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WG 3	includes contacts of people involved in WG
perceive-wg4-photos@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WG 4	includes contacts of people involved in WG
perceive-wg5-digitalart@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com	WG 5	includes contacts of people involved in WG

Table 8. People involved in the project.

Annex III contains the names of each mailing list participant.

External communication strategy: social media and website

The Communication strategy will act at internal and external level providing a support tool for communication activities, in order to increase both coordination among the partners identifying a common language useful to achieve the expected results and high visibility to the project activities and outputs ensuring high level of accessibility and understanding to all targets. Internal communication focuses on ensuring a good collaboration system, defining punctual workflow and a reporting system among Partners. Partners must be aware of the purpose and their fundamental role in increasing the impact and visibility of the project.

A [google form](#) was prepared, accessible for the partners, as the most appropriate instrument to facilitate the flow of information, simplifying the work and furthering relations and contribution of all the partners involved in the project implementation. Good internal communication management within the partnership is a key for the successful external communication of the project. To invite partners to submit content for dissemination through social channels, a document was prepared with guidelines to follow. The document is available in **Annex 1**.

External communication, on the other hand, aims at spreading project outputs and results throughout the included regions and to raise awareness in a wider audience of the included area. Main tool for external communication will be the official web platform.

The following social profiles are opened [Facebook](#), [Instagram](#), [Twitter](#), [Linkedin](#).

Telegram: Telegram channel “PERCEIVE” where we will send information and links of interest so that all partners are kept up to date with the activities taking place. The goal is then to broaden the audience beyond the partners involved in the project and make it a channel for communicating the possible technologies available for Cultural Heritage.

The YouTube channel will be open in the following month.

The Editorial Board decided to publish minimum **at least one post per week**, on the project channels:

1. Instagram, LinkedIn and Facebook: text with 1to2 images or/and short videos. The same text can be used for these three channels. In case the news is on the website insert the link;
2. Twitter: short text with image, insert link with details.

Content to be shared weekly can be under one of the following categories:

- **#perceiveeurope:** General post for the stack-holder to identify us.
- **#PerceivePartner:** post introducing the project partners, with link to the page on the Perceive website;
- **#PerceiveScenarios:** presentation of the 5 scenarios and case studies related to each scenario;
- **#PerceivePublication:** presentation of papers, popular and scientific that involved the project;
- **#PerceiveOnTheRoad:** story about the acquisition campaigns done/to be done in partner museums.

It is preferably published on **Fridays**, starting the first week of April.

All project partners will always be tagged in posts, and partners will always be reminded to share posts from personal and institutional profiles.

Website strategy:

1st year website:

- Develop the website with five sections (Home, Project, Contact, Partners, News)
- Presentation of the Horizon Europe project.
- Link to social media created.
- Present each partner and describe their expertise.
- From the Naples meeting display short videos and photos.
- One news per month about the project from each partner.
- Display conferences, meetings and scientific articles organized in Horizon Europe frame.
- Communication campaigns.

2nd year website:

- One news per month about the project from each partner.
- Put short videos and photos of the PERCEIVE events.
- Communication campaigns.
- Display conferences, meetings and scientific articles organized in Horizon Europe frame.
- Gate to the Repo, Tools, Services and Prototypes.

3rd year portal:

- The Platform accessed through the website, will be the gate to the Repo, Tools, Services and Prototypes.
- One of the pages of the project website will contain an overview and archive of all published information: scientific articles, publications, press releases, etc.
- Videos and examples of the prototypes applied to case studies.

Visual Communication strategy

In the frame of this strategy, ANAMNESIA has developed a Visual Strategy. Within this strategy, several activities have been carried out or they are foreseen:

Logo creation (color and black and white).

We have created variants and a single Icon that will represent in short, the project (The Perceive Eye).

Graphics for the website and specifically the HomePage.

Icons corresponding to the five scenarios: polychromy, painting, textiles, historic photos and digital art.

Graphics for the Webinars and Videos (video format)

Promo video trailer based on the storyboard available on the [Cordis](#) website.

In progress.

Graphics for the Posters and Flyers.

Annexes

I. Template for the Periodic Report (Technical Report Part A and Part B) and for the Financial Report “HEU_PERCEIVE_PR”

We report here only the cover and index of the template.

The entire template has been made available to all partners in the common SharePoint (../templates/)

Project: GA 101061157 — PERCEIVE — CALL: HORIZON-CL2-2021-HERITAGE-01

This project has received funding from the European Union’s HORIZON-CL2-2021-HERITAGE-01 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101061157

PERCEIVE

Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections
through AI and Virtual Experiences

Periodic Report

Technical Report (Part A)

Technical Report (Part B)

Financial Report

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II. Calculation model for Financial Report “HEU_PERCEIVE_FR_Partner”

Participant	Estimated expenditure								Estimated income					Total estimated income	
	A. Personnel costs	B. Subcontracting costs	C.1 Travel and subsistence	C.2 Purchase costs	C.3 Equipment	C.4 Other goods, works and services	E.1 Intensity Invited goods and services	E. Indirect costs	Funding rate	Requested EU contribution to eligible costs	Requested EU contribution to eligible costs	% in the project per participant	Revenues Income generated by the action		Other sources of financing Financial contributions
1 CNR	€ 383.807,00	€ -	€ 18.000	€ 30.000	€ 4.500	N/A	€ 109.075,75	€ 585.383,75	100%	€ 585.383,75	€ 585.383,75	15%			€ 585.383,75
2 FORTH	€ 500.000,00	€ -	€ 15.000	€ -	€ -	N/A	€ 128.750,00	€ 643.750,00	100%	€ 643.750,00	€ 643.750,00	17%			€ 643.750,00
3 Anamnesia	€ 63.942,00	€ -	€ 7.500	€ 30.000	€ -	N/A	€ 25.360,50	€ 126.802,50	100%	€ 126.802,50	€ 126.802,50	3%			€ 126.802,50
3.1 IMKI	€ 289.274,00	€ -	€ 7.500	€ -	€ -	N/A	€ 75.193,50	€ 375.967,50	100%	€ 375.967,50	€ 375.967,50	10%			€ 375.967,50
4 NTHU	€ 539.000,00	€ -	€ 15.000	€ -	€ 7.000	N/A	€ 140.250,00	€ 701.250,00	100%	€ 701.250,00	€ 701.250,00	19%			€ 701.250,00
5 FRAUNHOFER	€ 980.621,00	€ -	€ 18.000	€ -	€ 4.500	N/A	€ 150.780,25	€ 753.901,25	100%	€ 753.901,25	€ 753.901,25	20%			€ 753.901,25
6 MIC-MANN	€ 155.800,00	€ -	€ 13.000	€ 33.000	€ -	N/A	€ 48.950,00	€ 246.750,00	100%	€ 246.750,00	€ 246.750,00	7%			€ 246.750,00
7 OSU-MUNCH	€ 142.843,00	€ -	€ 6.000	€ 30.000	€ -	N/A	€ 69.720,75	€ 348.553,75	100%	€ 348.553,75	€ 348.553,75	9%			€ 348.553,75
8 AIC							€ -	€ -	100%	€ -	€ -	0%			€ -
9 Hoverlay							€ -	€ -	100%	€ -	€ -	0%			€ -
10 HSLU							€ -	€ -	100%	€ -	€ -	0%	€ 880.566,00		€ 880.566,00
11 V&A							€ -	€ -	100%	€ -	€ -	0%	€ 195.500,00		€ 195.500,00
TOTAL	2.757.287,00	40.000,00	100.000,00	113.000,00	26.000,00	0,00	749.071,75	3.785.358,75	0,00	3.785.358,75	3.785.358,75	100%	-	€ 1.076.066,00	€ 4.861.424,75
% in the project by cost category	73%	1%	3%	3%	1%	0%	20%	100%							

Participant	SUMMARY OF STAFF EFFORT								Total Person-Months per Participant	% in the project per participant
	WP 1	WP 2	WP 3	WP 4	WP 5	WP 6	WP 7	WP 8		
1 CNR	20,00	11,00	13,00	3,00	15,00	7,00	15,00	18,00	90,00	17%
2 FORTH	3,00	8,00	16,00	12,00	20,00	4,00	8,00	7,00	78,00	15%
3 Anamnesia	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	2,00	10,00	2%
3.1 IMKI	1,00	2,00	0,00	20,00	10,00	3,00	1,00	12,00	49,00	9%
4 NTHU	1,00	6,00	10,00	10,00	15,00	4,00	15,00	8,00	69,00	13%
5 FRAUNHOFER	10,00	4,00	3,00	30,00	11,00	8,00	4,00	6,00	76,00	14%
6 MIC-MANN	2,00	4,00	3,00	0,00	0,00	8,00	4,00	12,00	33,00	6%
7 OSU-MUNCH	0,50	5,00	4,50	0,00	0,00	7,50	4,00	7,00	28,50	5%
8 AIC	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,00	0,80	0,20	2,00	0%
9 Hoverlay	0,00	1,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	1,00	0,50	3,00	5,50	1%
10 HSLU	1,00	5,00	0,00	1,00	8,00	32,00	12,00	7,00	66,00	12%
11 V&A	2,00	5,00	3,00	0,00	0,00	9,00	5,00	4,00	28,00	5%
TOTAL	40,50	51,00	52,50	75,00	67,00	100,50	61,30	86,20	535,00	100%

MONTHS	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41
Reporting Period	First Reporting Period															Second Reporting Period																									
Milestones	M1															M2																									
Portal opening																																									
Preparation of Report																																									
Submission of Report																																									
Payment (if due)																																									
Internal Financial Management	First Internal Reporting Period															Second Internal Reporting Period																									
Internal Progress Report																																									

INSTRUCTIONS
 - Download the financial identification form at the following link; complete and sign it for each financial report
 - Complete the table below in accordance with the form

Download here the EU financial identification form

Select	Short name	
	PIC	#N/D
	Legal name	#N/D
	ACCOUNT NAME ②	
BANKING DETAILS ①	IBAN/ACCOUNT NUMBER ③	
	CURRENCY	
	BIC/SWIFT CODE	
	BRANCH CODE ④	
ADDRESS OF BANK BRANCH	BANK NAME	
	STREET & NUMBER	
	TOWN/CITY	
	POSTCODE	
ACCOUNT HOLDER'S DATA	COUNTRY	
	ACCOUNT HOLDER	
	STREET & NUMBER	
VAT number	TOWN/CITY	
	POSTCODE	
	COUNTRY	

III. MAILING LISTS SUMMARY

General Assembly [GA] Mailing List

mail: perceive-ga@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

The members are those listed in the Consortium Agreement. If modifications need to be made, a request to the project manager should be done. If there are two members in the list, this means that in case one of them cannot attend, the second may join.

MEMBERS:

- Pescarin Sofia CNR Coord
- Cerato Ivana CNR Manager
- Sotiropoulou FORTH
- Sappa ANAMNESIA
- Michel IMKI
- Graf FRAUNHOFER
- Verri AIC
- Sandu MUNCH
- Hardeberg NTNU
- Burgio V&A
- Robbe HOVERLAY
- Giulierini MANN
- Barandoni MANN
- Clay HSLU

Project Management Board [PMB] Mailing List

mail: perceive-pmb@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

The members are those listed in the Consortium Agreement. If modifications need to be made, a request to the project manager should be done. If there are two members in the list, this means that in case one of them cannot attend, the second may join.

MEMBERS

- Sofia Pescarin /CNR [co]
- Ivana Cerato / CNR [manager]
- Rojtberg Pavel - FRAUNH Sc. Coord.
- Holger Graf /Fraunhofer [wp4]
- Paolo Giulierini-Cristiana Barandoni /MANN [wp2]
- Sophia Sotiropoulou /FORTH [wp3, wp5]
- Jon Yngve Hardeberg /NTNU [wp7]
- Simon Sappa /Anamnesia [Inn. wp8]
- Laura Martel /Imki [Inn. wp8]

Project Scientific Board [PSB] Mailing List

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The members are those listed in the Consortium Agreement. If modifications need to be made, a request to the project manager should be done. If there are two members in the list, this means that in case one of them cannot attend, the second may join.

MEMBERS:

- Rojtberg Pavel - FRAUNH Sc. Coord.
- Pescarin Sofia - CNR Coord.
- Cerato Ivana - CNR wp1
- Barandoni Cristiana - MANN - wp2
- Sophia Sotiropoulou - FORTH - wp3
- Sinha Neil - FRAUNH - wp4
- Trahanias Panos - FORTH - wp5
- Emmanouil Sylligardos - FORTH - wp5
- Ferdani Daniele - CNR - wp6
- George Sony - NTNU - wp7
- Martel Laura - IMKI - wp8
- Sappa Simon - ANAMNESIA - wp8

Working Groups Reference Partners:

- Verri Giovanni - AIC - WG1
- Donata Magrini - CNR - WG1
- Sandu Irina - MUNCH - WG2
- Monico Letizia - CNR - WG2
- Burgio Lucia - V&A - WG3/WG4
- Giorgio Trumpy - NTNU - WG3
- Brenda Doherty - CNR - WG3
- Clay Arthur - HSLU - WG5

Invited from PMB:

- Graf Holger - FRAUNH.
- Hardeberg Jon – NTNU

WP 1 – Coordination

perceive-wp1@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

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- Pescarin Sofia - CNR ISPC
- Massi Benedetti Cristina - CNR ISPC
- Vanessa Bonanno – CNR ISPC
- Graf Holger - FRAUNH
- Sotiropoulou Sophia - FORTH
- Barandoni Cristiana - MANN

WP 2 – User needs and requirements

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- Barandoni Cristiana - MANN
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- Cerato Ivana - CNR IS
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- Ferdani Daniele - CNR ISPC
- Magrini, Donata - CNR ISPC
- Samuele Spotti – CNR ISPC
- Manganelli del Fà Rachele - CNR ISPC
- Vanessa Bonanno – CNR ISPC
- Clay Arthur – HSLU
- Huwiler, Ariana – HSLU
- Woods, Janina – HSLU
- Lanfranconi, Dario - HSLU
- Michel Florent - IMKI
- Graf Holger – FRAUNH
 - Rücker, Fabian - FRAUNH
- Verri Giovanni - AIC
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- Ciortan Irina - NTNU
- Arteaga Yoko – NTNU
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- Trahanias Panos - FORTH
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- Stavroulakis Petros – FORTH
- Sigalas Markos - FORTH
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- Papadopoulos, George - FORTH
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WP 3 – Data

perceive-wp3@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

- Pescarin Sofia - CNR ISPC
- Buti David - CNR ISPC
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- Miliani Costanza - CNR ISPC
- Doherty Brenda - CNR SCITEC
- Monico Letizia - CNR SCITEC
- Sotiropoulou Sophia - FORTH

- Hatzigiannakis, Kostas - FORTH
- Sigalas, Markos – FORTH
- Papadopoulos, George - FORTH
- Dialektakis, George - FORTH
- Stavroulakis, Petros - FORTH
- Sylligardos, Emmanouil - FORTH
- Trahanias, Panos - FORTH
- George, Sony - NTNU
- Hardeberg, Jon Yngve - NTNU
- Pedersen, Marius - NTNU
- Marcos Xose, Alvarez Cid - NTNU
- Trumpy, Giorgio - NTNU
- Sinha, Saptarshi Neil - FRAUNH
- Barandoni, Cristiana - MANN
- Sandu, Irina Crina Anca - MUNCH
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- Burgio, Lucia - V&A

WP 4 – AI/IBR

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- GRAF, Holger - FRAUNH
- Sinha, Saptarshi Neil - FRAUNH
- Rojtberg, Pavel - FRAUNH
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- Cerato, Ivana - CNR ISPC
- Fanini, Bruno - CNR ISPC
- Sotiropoulou Sophia - FORTH
- Sigalas, Markos - FORTH
- Stavroulakis, Petros - FORTH
- Sylligardos, Emmanouil – FORTH
- Dialektakis, George - FORTH
- Papadopoulos, George - FORTH
- Trahanias, Panos - FORTH
- Michel, Florent - IMKI
- Trumpy, Giorgio - NTNU
- Robbe, Nicolas - HOVERLAY

WP 5 – Platform

perceive-wp5@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

- Pescarin, Sofia - CNR ISPC
- Cerato, Ivana - CNR ISPC
- Fanini, Bruno - CNR ISPC
- Ferdani, Daniele - CNR ISPC

- Marcello Massidda - CNR ISPC
- Samuele Spotti – CNR ISPC
- Vanessa Bonanno – CNR ISPC
- Michel, Florent – IMKI
- Martel, Laura - IMKI
- Trumpy, Giorgio - NTNU
- Graf, Holger - FRAUNH
- Pöllabauer, Thomas - FRAUNH
- Rojtberg, Pavel - FRAUNH
- Rücker, Fabian - FRAUNH
- Sinha, Saptarshi Neil - FRAUNH
- Sigalas, Markos - FORTH
- Dialektakis, George - FORTH
- Trahanias, Panos - FORTH
- Stavroulakis, Petros - FORTH
- Sylligardos, Emmanouil – FORTH
- Papadopoulos, George - FORTH
- Robbe, Nicolas – HOVERLAY
- Aga, Birgitte Cathrine – MUNCH
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- Huwiler, Ariana - HSLU
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WP 6 – Prototypes and Experiences

perceive-wp6@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

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- Magrini, Donata - CNR ISPC
- Manganelli Del Fà, Rachele - CNR ISPC
- Pietroni, Eva - CNR ISPC
- D'Annibale, Enzo - CNR ISPC
- Palombini, Augusto - CNR ISPC
- Samuele Spotti – CNR ISPC
- Vanessa Bonanno – CNR ISPC
- Barandoni Cristiana - MANN
- Sotiropoulou, Sophia - FORTH
- Stavroulakis, Petros - FORTH
- Trahanias, Panos – FORTH
- Sigalas Markos - FORTH
- Dialektakis, George - FORTH
- Papadopoulos, George - FORTH

- Michel, Florent - IMKI
- Martel, Laura - IMKI
- Simon, Sappa - Anamnesia
- Trumpy, Giorgio - NTNU
- Arteaga, Yoko - NTNU
- Ciortan, Irina - NTNU
- GRAF, Holger - FRAUNH
- Rücker, Fabian - FRAUNH
- Sivert, Espen Iglebæk Thue - MUNCH
- Aga, Birgitte Cathrine – MUNCH
- Sandu, Irina Crina Anca - MUNCH
- Verri, Giovanni - AIC
- Clay, Arthur - HSLU
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WP 7 – Evaluation

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- Magrini, Donata - CNR ISPC
- Bonanno, Vanessa - CNR ISPC
- Manganelli Del Fà, Rachele - CNR ISPC
- Pagano, Alfonsina - CNR ISPC
- Samuele Spotti – CNR ISPC
- Sotiropoulou, Sophia - FORTH
- Stavroulakis, Petros - FORTH
- Trahanias, Panos – FORTH
- Sigalas Markos - FORTH
- Dialektakis, George - FORTH
- Papadopoulos, George - FORTH
- Huwiler, Ariana - HSLU
- Woods, Janina – HSLU
- Lanfranconi, Dario - HSLU
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WP 8 – Dissemination and Innovation

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- Martel, Laura - IMKI
- Michel, Florent - IMKI
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- Pescarin, Sofia - CNR ISPC
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- Manganelli Del Fà, Rachele - CNR ISPC
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- Pietroni, Eva - CNR ISPC
- Samuele Spotti – CNR ISPC
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- GRAF, Holger - FRAUNH
- Rucker, Fabian - FRAUNH
- Barandoni, Cristiana - MANN
- Sandu, Irina Crina Anca - MUNCH
- Verri, Giovanni - AIC
- Robbe, Nicolas - Hoverlay
- Clay, Arthur – HSLU
- Huwiler, Ariana – HSLU
- Woods, Janina - HSLU
- Lanfranconi, Dario - HSLU
- Trumpy, Giorgio - NTNU
- Hardeberg, Jon Yngve – NTNU
- George, Sony – NTNU
- Burgio, Lucia - V&A
- Trahanias, Panos – FORTH
- Sotiropoulou, Sophia – FORTH
- Pouli, Paraskevi – FORTH
- Papadopoulos, George - FORTH
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- Sigalas Markos - FORTH

WORKING GROUP 1 – polychromy

perceive-wg1-polychromy@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

- Ferdani, Daniele - CNR ISPC
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- Magrini, Donata - CNR ISPC
- Palombini, Augusto - CNR ISPC
- Samuele, Spotti - CNR ISPC
- Vanessa Bonanno – CNR ISPC
- Barandoni, Cristiana - MANN
- GRAF, Holger – FRAUNH
- Pöllabauer, Thomas - FRAUNH
- Rojtberg, Pavel - FRAUNH
- Sinha, Saptarshi Neil - FRAUNH
- Stavroulakis, Petros - FORTH
- Sotiropoulou, Sophia - FORTH
- Verri, Giovanni - AIC
- Liverani, Paolo UNIFI
- Sigalas, Markos – FORTH
- Dialektakis, George - FORTH
- Trahanias, Panos – FORTH
- Papadopoulos, George - FORTH
- Sylligardos, Emmanouil – FORTH
- Arthur Clay - HSLU

WORKING GROUP 2 – paintings

perceive-wg2-paintings@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

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- Miliani, Costanza - CNR ISPC
- Cerato Ivana – CNR ISPC
- Magrini, Donata - CNR ISPC
- Buti, David - CNR ISPC
- Pietroni, Eva - CNR ISPC
- Monico, Letizia - CNR SCITEC
- Doherty Brenda - CNR SCITEC
- Veggi, Manuele - CNR ISPC
- Bonanno, Vanessa - CNR ISPC
- Samuele Spotti – CNR ISPC
- Aga, Birgitte Cathrine – MUNCH
- Sandu, Irina Crina Anca - MUNCH
- Clay, Arthur – HSLU
- Trumpy, Giorgio – NTNU
- Ciortan Irina - NTNU
- George, Sony – NTNU
- Arteaga, Yoko - NTNU
- Rojtberg, Pavel – FRAUNH
- Sotiropoulou Sophia - FORTH
- Stavroulakis Petros - FORTH
- Verri, Giovanni - AIC

WORKING GROUP 3 – textiles

perceive-wg3-textiles@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

- Doherty Brenda - CNR SCITEC
- Monico, Letizia - CNR SCITEC
- Miliani, Costanza – CNR ISPC
- Cerato Ivana – CNR ISPC
- Magrini, Donata - CNR ISPC
- Buti, David - CNR ISPC
- Travaglini, Laura - CNR ISPC
- Samuele Spotti – CNR ISPC
- Vanessa Bonanno – CNR ISPC
- Aga, Birgitte Cathrine – MUNCH
- Clay, Arthur – HSLU
- Martel, Laura - IMKI
- Burgio, Lucia V&A
- Sotiropoulou Sophia - FORTH
- Stavroulakis Petros - FORTH
- George, Sony - NTNU
- Kutzke, Hartmut

WORKING GROUP 4 – photos

perceive-wg4-photos@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

- Fanini, Bruno – CNR ISPC
- Cerato Ivana – CNR ISPC
- Magrini Donata – CNR ISPC
- Samuele Spotti – CNR ISPC
- Vanessa Bonanno – CNR ISPC
- Michel Florent - IMKI
- Trumpy, Giorgio - NTNU
- GRAF, Holger - FRAUNH
- Sigalas, Markos – FORTH
- Dialektakis, George - FORTH
- Trahanias, Panos – FORTH
- Papadopoulos, George - FORTH
- Sylligardos, Emmanouil - FORTH
- Stavroulakis Petros - FORTH
- Rojtberg, Pavel - FRAUNH
- Sotiropoulou Sophia - FORTH
- Sinha, Saptarshi Neil - FRAUNH
- Arthur Clay - HSLU
- Robbe, Nicolas – HOVERLAY

WORKING GROUP 5 – digitalart

perceive-wg5-digitalart@cnrsc.onmicrosoft.com

- Clay, Arthur - HSLU
- Pescarin, Sofia - CNR ISPC
- Magrini, Donata - CNR ISPC
- Massidda, Marcello- CNR ISPC
- Pietroni, Eva- CNR ISPC
- D'Annibale, Enzo - CNR ISPC
- Travaglini, Laura- CNR ISPC
- Bonanno, Vanessa - CNR ISPC
- Spotti, Samuele - CNR ISPC
- Sandu, Irina- MUNCH
- Aga, Birgitte Cathrine – MUNCH
- Burgio, Lucia - V&A
- Laura, Martel- IMKI
- Robbe, Nicolas - Hoverlay